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Assess the Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Cervical Cancer Among Women in Selected Rural Areas of Kollam District

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ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer is the second common female malignant tumour globally which seriously threatens female's health. Persistent infection of high-risk Human papilloma virus (HPV) has been clarified to be the necessary cause of cervical cancer. This study was to assess the level of knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women in selected rural areas of Kollam district of South Kerala; to determine the correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women in selected rural areas, to determine the association between knowledge regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables and to find out the association between attitude regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables. This cross-sectional study was conducted among women of age group 35-65 years who were residing Pampuram ward (number 10) of Kalluvathukkal panchayat of Kollam district in South Kerala during the period of 2024-2025. Socio personal data sheet was used to collect socio demographic data of women's age group of 35 -65 years. Knowledge questionnaire was used to assess the knowledge regarding cervical cancer. 5-point Likert scale was used to assess the attitude of women regarding cervical cancer. The result of the study showed that 52% of the women had average knowledge, 40% had poor knowledge, 8% had good knowledge, and 84% had average attitude, 11% had poor attitude and 5% had good attitude regarding cervical cancer. Age, religion, education, occupation, marital status, number of children, and monthly family income did not

significantly correlate with either knowledge or attitude. Women's attitudes and knowledge

about cervical cancer showed a weakly positive correlation.

Keywords: *Women, cervical cancer, knowledge, attitude*

INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer is the second common female malignant tumour globally which seriously threatens female's health. Persistent infection of high-risk Human papilloma virus (HPV) has been clarified to be the necessary cause of cervical cancer. The development and implementation of an all-encompassing cervical cancer prevention and control strategy were expedited by the unambiguous Etiology [1].

A woman's cervix—the opening from the vagina to the uterus—is where cervical cancer first appears. 99% of occurrences of cervical cancer are associated with high-risk human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, an extremely common virus transmitted through sexual contact. Although most infections with HPV resolve spontaneously and cause no symptoms, persistent infection can cause cervical cancer in women[2].

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer in women. In 2022, an estimated 6,60,000 women were diagnosed with cervical cancer worldwide and about 3,50,000 women died from the disease. The majority of occurrences of cervical cancer can be avoided with effective primary (HPV vaccine) and secondary preventive strategies (screening for and treating precancerous lesions). As long as it is identified early and properly treated, cervical cancer is one of the most treatable types of cancer. With the right therapy and palliative care, late-stage cancers can also be managed. Cervical cancer can be eradicated as a public health issue in a generation with a comprehensive strategy to prevention, screening, and treatment [3].

More than 70 nations and worldwide academic associations responded favourably to the World Health Organization's (WHO) May 2018 call for the universal eradication of cervical cancer. Following that, on November 17, 2020, the World Health Organization published a global strategy to expedite the eradication of cervical cancer as a public health issue in order to pave the way for future cervical cancer prevention and control. As a result, 194 nations pledged to eradicate cervical cancer for the first time. At this milestone time point, we reviewed the update progress of cervical cancer prevention and control in epidemiology, risk factors and screening, in order to pave the way of cervical cancer elimination[4].

According to statistics from 2018, 96,922 new cases of cervical cancer are diagnosed in India each year. Although the number of occurrences of cervical cancer is decreasing in the industrialized world, poorer nations are still heavily burdened by the disease., where the risk of developing Cervical Cancer is 35% greater compared to developed countries. About 25% of global mortality due to Cervical Cancer occurs in India[5].

Because cervical cancer has a lengthy pre-invasive phase, it is curable. Reducing death rates from cervical cancer in women requires early identification and treatment. Fortunately, there is a lengthy premalignant period for cervical cancer, which allows for screening and treatment before the disease develops into invasive cervical cancer [6].

In a survey on breast and cervical cancer among women in 12 districts of Kerala, the Kerala Health Department discovered that

0.71% of 7,06,275 women who were 30 years of age or older were at risk for cervical cancer [7]. Kerala health department begins a campaign focuses on cervical cancer awareness from February 4, 2025 onwards for screening the cervical cancer among women aged above 35 years [7] On review of literature it is found that there is a paucity of studies done among knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women aged above 35 years residing in southern Kerala so, following this study, we tend to give them proper awareness regarding the cervical cancer and its screening methods through our community health department and ASHA workers and providing them awareness pamphlet, also planned community level awareness classes in nearby primary health centres by community health department of N S Memorial College of Nursing, Kollam for women's age between 35-65 years who following this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

We conducted a descriptive study, surveying a non-probability convenience sampling technique of 100 women's age between 35-65 were selected for this study based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Women who aged between 35 to 65 years residing in Pampuram ward (number 10) of Kalluvathukkal Panchayat were selected for this study.

Method of Data Collection

Women age between 35-65 residing in Pampuram village were selected, after obtaining the due consent from them. Two tools were used in this study Tool 1: Socio personal data sheet; A socio personal data sheet will be used to gather information regarding the socio personal variables. The socio personal data sheet related to socio personal factors including, Socio demographic data sheet section A has 8 questions regarding the demographic data of women, which includes age, religion,

education, occupation, marital status, number of children, family monthly income, and source of health information's and section B was knowledge questionnaire it contains 20 interview questions, were assess the knowledge regarding cervical cancer. It includes questions regarding anatomy of cervix, functions of cervix, definition of cervical cancer, causative factors, risk factors, clinical manifestations, diagnostic measures, treatment, prevention and side effects of cervical cancer. Scoring of 0-6 poor, 7-13 average, 14-20 good.

Tool 2: 5-point Likert scale, Likert scale is a psychometric scale used to measure attitudes, opinions, or perceptions by asking respondents to indicate their level of agreement or satisfaction with a statement. In this study, researchers use 5-point Likert scale which includes 6 positive statements and 4 negative statements. The points are strongly agreed (score 4), agree (score 3), uncertain (score 2), disagree (score 1) and strongly disagree (score 0). Technique used was self-report method.

Statistical Analysis

The data was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The relationship between women's knowledge and attitudes about cervical cancer in particular rural locations was evaluated using the Karl Pearson correlation coefficient. The Chi square test was utilized to determine the relationship between certain demographic variables and awareness about cervical cancer, as well as the relationship between sociodemographic variables and attitude. All analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26.

RESULTS

The results of this study were discussed under the following headings. 1. Distribution of sample characteristics

based on socio demographic variables 2. Knowledge of women regarding cervical cancer 3. Attitude of women regarding cervical cancer 4. Correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women in selected rural areas. 5. Association between knowledge regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables. 7. Association between attitude regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables.

In this study among 100 women, 38% of women belong to the age group of 35-45 years, 32% belong to 46-55 years, and 30% belongs to 56-65 years. Among the women, 92% were Hindus, 4% were Muslims, and 4% were Christians. In this study, majority (69%) of the respondents had primary education followed by

graduates (26%). Respondents who were illiterate composed of 1% and others of 4%. Study revealed that among 100, women majority (82%) of the women were housewife. 8% were self-employed, 8% were private employee, and 2% were government employee. Majority (86%) of the women were married, 9% were widow and 5% were unmarried. Majority (81%) of the women had 1 or 2 children, 13% had 3 or more children, and 6% had no children. Based on the monthly family income, 48% of women had monthly family income in between 5001-10000, 35% had monthly family income of <5000, and 17% had monthly family income >10000. Among the 100 women, 41% of women got health information from health care personnel, and 59% women never received any health information.

Section A: Distribution of sample characteristics based on socio demographic variables.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of women based on age (in years). n=100

Age in Years	f	%
35-45 years	38	38%
46-55 years	32	32%
56-65 years	30	30%

n=100

Fig. 1: Percentage distribution of women based on Religion.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of women based on education. n=100

Education	f	%
Illiterate	1	1
Primary education	69	69
Graduate	26	26
Others	4	4

n=100

Fig. 2: Frequency and percentage distribution of women based on occupation.

Table 3: Frequency and percentage distribution of women based on previous information. n=100

Previous information	f	%
Yes	49	49%
No	51	51%

Section B: Knowledge of Women Regarding Cervical Cancer

Table 4: Frequency and percentage distribution of the women according to knowledge regarding cervical cancer. n=100

Sl. No.	Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
1	Poor	40	40%
2	Average	52	52%
3	Good	8	8%
	Total	100	100

Table 5: Mean and Standard deviation of knowledge regarding cervical cancer among women. n= 100

Variable	Mean	SD	Maximum	Minimum
Knowledge	7.71	3.50	16	1

Section C: Attitude of Women Regarding Cervical Cancer

Table 6: Frequency and percentage distribution of women according to attitude regarding cervical cancer. n=100

Sl. no	Attitude	Frequency	Percentage
1	Poor	11	11%
2	Average	84	84%
3	Good	5	5%
	Total	100	100%

Table 7: Mean and standard deviation of attitude regarding cervical cancer among women. n=100

Variable	Mean	SD	Maximum	Minimum
Attitude	24.37	3.20	32	17

Section D: Correlation between Knowledge and Attitude Regarding Cervical Cancer among Women in Selected Rural Areas

Table 8: Mean, standard deviation and correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women. n=100

Variables	Mean	Standard deviation	Correlation	P value
Knowledge	7.71	3.50	0.127	0.209
Attitude	24.37	3.20	0.127	0.209

There was a significant weak positive ($r=0.127$, $p=0.209$) correlation between knowledge and attitude of women regarding cervical cancer which indicates as the knowledge increases, attitude also increases. Hence the hypothesis H1 was accepted.

Section E: Association between Knowledge Regarding Cervical Cancer and Selected Demographic Variables

Table 9: Table depicting association between knowledge regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables. n=100

Sl.no.	Socio demographic Variables	df	χ^2	P value
1	Age	4	6.343	0.175
2	Religion	4	1.750	0.782
3	Education	6	4.595	0.597
4	Occupation	6	4.310	0.635
5	Marital status	4	2.508	0.643
6	No. of children	4	1.611	0.807
7	Family monthly income	4	5.508	0.239
8	Previous knowledge	2	3.344	0.188

The attitude of women regarding cervical cancer and selected socio demographic variables shows no significant association and hence the hypothesis H3 was rejected.

DISCUSSION

This cross-sectional study was conducted among women of age group 35-65 years who were residing Pampuram ward (number 10) of Kalluvathukkal panchayat of Kollam district in South Kerala during the period of 2024-2025. The present study was aimed to assess the knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women age between 35-65. This study provides a detailed information regarding how much the women were aware about this cervical cancer. Cervical cancer remains a significant health concern in India. According to human papilloma virus Centre's 2023 Report, there were 1,23,907 new cases and 77,348 deaths due to cervical Cancer in India in 2020[8]. In Kerala health department conducted a survey regarding breast and cervical cancer among women across 12 districts in Kerala, found that 0.71% of 7,06,275 women aged 30 and above were identified being at risk of cervical cancer[7]. This study provides information regarding current awareness, attitude and practice about Cervical Cancer and screening, which is helpful for designing population-based educational program leading to knowledge enhancement about Cervical Cancer and its screening.

The present study revealed that among 100 women, 52% had average knowledge and 84% had average attitude regarding cervical cancer. In a cross-sectional study conducted to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice towards cervical cancer among women attending obstetrics and gynaecology department in South India. 74.6% were knowledgeable regarding cervical cancer and 62.5% had positive attitude regarding cervical cancer[9]. It was congruent with the present study findings. A study was conducted on knowledge, attitude towards cervical cancer among female university students in a South Africa in 2009, discovered that while 97% of participants

had heard of cervical cancer, only 26% were aware of pap smears, and their understanding of screening and preventative procedures was inadequate. It was consistent with the results of the current investigation.[10] In a 2013 study, women who visited a teaching hospital in Nepal were asked about their knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding cervical cancer screening. found that only 40% had adequate knowledge and 18% ever had a pap smear test[11]. It was incongruent with present study findings.

Limitations of this study found to be Possibility of participants dishonesty and lack of seriousness in answering questions and study is limited time and resources, the result of the study cannot be generalized since it is a small sample size, it can be conducted as interventional study, on a large sample which might yield more reliable results. Knowledge and awareness among women's age between 35-65 may differ in different residing areas and settings and therefore study may be conducted with representative samples from urban and other rural areas from Kollam district.

CONCLUSION

In this present study Mean, standard deviation and correlation between knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer among women showed that there was a significant weak positive ($r=0.127$, $p=0.209$) correlation between knowledge and attitude of women regarding cervical cancer which indicates as the knowledge increases, attitude also increases. Association between knowledge regarding cervical cancer and selected demographic variables showed that the knowledge of women regarding cervical cancer and selected socio demographic variables found no significant association. The findings of this study may provide information that, among the women of Pampuram ward (number 10) of

Kalluvathukkal village, majority were having average knowledge and average attitude regarding cervical cancer. In order to increase the knowledge and attitude regarding cervical cancer, we conducted an awareness program regarding cervical cancer with the help of brochure.

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